

Accuracy analysis for GAIA97

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1. Introduction

The note 'Design and performance of the GAIA97 instrument' (Bastian & Roeser, 2 July 1997) contains an assessment of the astrometric performance for a specific optical/detector configuration. Applying the accuracy analysis method described in gaia_ll_1 and used in subsequent gaia_ll notes, I obtain astrometric errors which are almost a factor 2 larger. The present note gives a more detailed account of my accuracy analysis as applied to GAIA97, including a strict evaluation of the Cramer-Rao bound. A lot of intermediate results are given, in the hope that a detailed comparison with the calculations of B&R will reveal the reasons for the discrepancy.

2. Assumptions

Mission: the mission length is 5 years with no dead time. The scan speed is 120 arcsec/s.

Optics: GAIA97 has 4 FOVs, each using a double square aperture of 0.5 m sidelength, giving an aperture area of 0.5 m² per FOV. The baselength (distance between the centres of the two squares) is 1 m. The focal length is 60 m. The total transmittance was set to 0.7762 (independent of wavelength) in order to reproduce the count rate in B&R.

Detector: the solid angle of the CCDs is 0.05 deg. The pixel size is 5*30 um. The basic integration time for each readout (i.e., crossing of a single CCD chip) is exactly 1.5 s, corresponding to 180 arcsec or 0.05236 m in the focal plane. The number of pixels across the CCD is then $0.05236/5E-6 = 10472$. The readout noise is 2 electrons RMS. QE versus wavelength is given in gaia_ll_7 (Table 1). However, only the range 400-1000 nm was used.

Object: an unreddened G2V star of magnitude V=15 was assumed. The relative energy distribution versus wavelength was taken from Gunn & Stryker for the G2V star HD 154760, scaled in such a way as to give V=15 for the standard V response curve. The zero point of the V scale was fixed by assuming a flux density of 3.693E-23 W/m²/Hz at 550 nm for an A0V star of V=0. Converted to photon fluxes this gives, for the V=15 G2V star, 78.4 ph/s/m²/nm at 400 nm, 103.3 at 500 nm, 107.8 at 550 nm, 108.6 at 600 nm, 104.2 at 700 nm, 99.1 at 800 nm, 83.3 at 900 nm, and 76.1 at 1000 nm (at the resolution of Gunn & Stryker, i.e., 2 to 4 nm).

Sky: a sky brightness of V=21.5 per arcsec² was assumed (with V-I=2) in order to reproduce the dark+sky count rate in B&R of 0.2 e/pixel/s. Two FOVs were superposed, i.e., each FOV contributed 0.1 e/pixel/s.

3. Total observing time, number of transits

The mean total observing time on any given object in one FOV is (mission length)*(FOV solid angle)/(sky solid angle) = $(5*365.35*86400)*0.05/41253 = 191.24$ s. For the 4 FOVs the number of transits (each of 1.5 s) is $4*191.24/1.5 = 510.0$ exactly as given by B&R.

4. Count rates and fringe image

B&R specifies a count rate of 1529300 e/s for a V=10 star. This could be exactly reproduced by assuming a total transmittance of 0.7763, giving 15293 Hz for V=15 without filters (or 14533 Hz in 400–1000 nm). The effective wavelength is 620 nm.

B&R assumes fringe dispersion with a resolution of 40 nm. The interval 600–640 nm was investigated in detail. In this interval the count rate was 1394 Hz, giving a total of 2091 (stellar) counts from a 1.5 s transit. The distribution of these 2091 counts along the pixels is given in Table 1 below. Coordinate $j=0$ means a pixel exactly centred on the central fringe; $j=1$ means the next pixel, and so on. The counts are symmetric around $j=0$. For both Cols 2 and 3 the sum over $j=-\infty$ to $+\infty$ would be 2091.

The calculations described below were made by including the sampling effects, i.e., the smearing of the fringes caused by the pixel width and the corresponding time window in the TDI mode. The resulting counts are given in Col 2 of Table 1. Later it was realised that the sampling effects were not included by B&R (TBC), and part of the calculations were re-done to verify that the sampling effects did not have a serious impact on the end results. Col 3 was obtained by excluding the sampling effects, i.e., by removing the sinc^2 factor in Equation (31) of `gaia_ll_1`.

The equivalent 'background' level from one CCD transit is 4.3 counts/pixel. This includes the sky count rate of 0.2 Hz times the 1.5 s integration, and the readout noise of 2 electrons RMS (adding the same noise as the Poisson noise of a constant background of 4 counts/pixel).

Table 1. Fringe image (counts per pixel) as function of offset coordinate j (in pixels). In Col 2 the averaging by the pixel width (in space and time) is included, in Col 3 this is not taken into account. The spectral interval is 600–640 nm.

j	C_j	$C_j(\text{no sampling effects})$
0	272.46	281.29
1	225.03	230.49
2	118.36	116.64
3	28.61	21.96
4	9.07	3.33
5	51.65	50.95
6	103.83	107.47
7	118.77	122.84
8	90.00	91.37
9	44.83	43.47
10	12.47	10.48
11	1.29	0.34
12	1.63	1.72
13	2.40	2.64
14	1.05	0.96
15	0.28	0.11
16	1.01	1.06
17	1.36	1.50
18	0.58	0.49
19	0.86	0.56
20	4.24	4.07

5. Cramer-Rao bound

The function C_j was actually computed with 8 times oversampling, i.e., for intervals of 0.125 in the pixel coordinate j (called x hereafter). Linear interpolation from these values provides a 'continuous' function $C(x)$ from which the CR bound can be evaluated.

In practice the integrals over x are truncated to the interval $[-x_{\max}, x_{\max}]$ where $x_{\max} = 0.0180 \times \lambda(\text{nm})$ is the position of the second minimum. For the spectral interval 600–640 nm, $x_{\max} = 11.2$ pixels and I find:

$$\text{INTEGRAL } C'(x)^2 / (b + C(x)) \, dx = 832 \text{ pixel}^{-2}$$

where $b=4.3$ is the equivalent background level. Hence the CR bound:

$$\text{sd}_{\text{CR}} = W * 832^{-1/2} = 596 \text{ uas}$$

where $W = 17189$ uas is the pixel width. The number of stellar counts actually used is slightly less than the total number 2091 in the image, viz.:

$$N_{\text{used}} = \text{INTEGRAL } C(x) dx = 1839 \text{ counts}$$

6. Simulation of location estimation

Poisson variates n with expectation $b + C(x - x_0)$ were generated for values of x_0 uniformly distributed in $[-0.5, 0.5]$. For each simulated CCD transit, the location x_0 was then estimated by maximizing the log-likelihood function, $\text{SUM } n \times \ln(b + C(x - x_0)) - (b + C(x - x_0))$, assuming $b + C(x)$ to be perfectly known. Only the three central fringes were used. From 25000 experiments, the RMS error in x_0 was found to be 591 uas, in very good agreement with the CR bound. It was verified that the location algorithm performed equally well in other spectral channels, i.e., within a few per cent of the CR bound.

These experiments can be seen as an independent check of the CR calculation, or as a demonstration that the CR can be reached by a real (and not very complicated) location algorithm in the present case of a well-sampled fringe image.

7. Location precision from approximate formula

In *gaia_ll_1* an approximate expression for the CR bound was derived, depending on a dimensionless constant k , which was taken to be about 0.5. In the above case of the spectral interval 600–640 nm this formula gives 793 uas with $k=0.5$, thus an overestimation of the CR bound by 33%. It was found that a value of $k=0.31$ could reproduce the CR bound rather well in the present case and also in other spectral channels for the same object. This is not a result that can be generalised to other fringe images, but it does indicate that estimates based on $k=0.5$ (e.g., in *gaia_ll_3* and *gaia_ll_6*) may be somewhat conservative.

8. Total precision for dispersed fringes

The calculation of the CR bound described above for the spectral channel 600–640 nm was repeated for all the 40 nm channels from 400 to 1000 nm. The results are summarised in Table 2. Designations are:

λ = wavelength region of the spectral channel (nm)

N_{tot} = total number of stellar counts per transit (1.5 s)
 N_{used} = number of stellar counts in the three central fringes
 sd_{CR} = CR bound of the location from one transit (uas)
 sd_{sim} = RMS location error from 25,000 Monte Carlo experiments (uas)
 sd_{xi} = location error according to `gaia_ll_1` with $k=0.31$ (approximate CR)

Table 2. Statistics for a single transit (1.5 s) of the star in each of the spectral channels, and (last line) for the case of no fringe dispersion. sd_{sim} was calculated only in a few cases as verification of sd_{CR} .

lambda	N_{tot}	N_{used}	sd_{CR}	sd_{sim}	sd_{xi}
400-440	1494	1352	532	525	536
440-480	1978	1778	487	-	499
480-520	2091	1879	502	-	520
520-560	2141	1925	526	-	550
560-600	2172	1952	552	-	582
600-640	2091	1880	596	591	631
640-680	2046	1839	636	-	676
680-720	1948	1751	689	-	733
720-760	1682	1512	787	-	836
760-800	1326	1193	949	-	1000
800-840	1011	909	1171	1174	1220
840-880	788	708	1433	-	1476
880-920	587	528	1811	-	1839
920-960	347	312	2707	-	2684
960-1000	165	148	4878	4985	4735
400-1000	21869	19624	244	244	220 (no fringe dispersion)

The total precision of a transit is obtained by adding the weights (sd^{-2}) of the channels and gives 181 uas from sd_{CR} , and 189 uas from sd_{xi} . The improvement due to fringe dispersion is a factor $181/244 = 0.74$ in the standard error.

The total sd_{CR} of 181 uas per transit corresponds to a parallax error of $2.0 * 181 / \sqrt{510} = 16.0$ uas, where 2.0 is the sky-averaged 'parallax factor' according to `gaia_ll_1`. For comparison, B&R gives 8.4 uas for the parallax precision. The discrepancy by a factor 1.9 needs to be explained.

Actually, if the sampling effects are removed from the present calculations (i.e., using Col 3 instead of Col 2 in Table 1), the sd_{CR} reduces to 533 uas in the 600-640 nm channel, and the total precision is probably reduced in proportion, i.e., to 162 uas per transit and 14.3 uas for the parallax. Thus the real discrepancy is rather a factor 1.7; still a bit too large for comfort.